

VARIETIES OF ENGLISH

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Annotation: According to the statistics provided by ThoughtCo¹, English as a Second Language is learned by 375 million people, while English as a Foreign Language is learnt by 750 million

Key Words: World, English, Publish, Information.

1 Introduction

This journal issue is a collection of articles that ponder the status, functions, and features of Englishes that in their home settings are mostly known as a foreign language.

They are normally used for intercultural communication with people of other countries and rarely for interpersonal communication within their own countries.

These varieties of English belong to the third group of Englishes that are regularly named Expanding Circle Englishes in the famous Three Circles Theory of Braj B. Kachru (1985)

¹ThoughtCo is a premier reference education site, whose content is created by high-grading experts in a field.

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The other two groups are termed Inner Circle Englishes, characterized as native (first) languages for the majority of their countries' populations and serving almost all possible functions within their communities, and Outer Circle Englishes, institutionalized and serving as a second official (co-official) language in their country's institutions.

The quantitative research conducted by Margie Berns in 2005 and 2019 demonstrated steadily growing interest in Expanding Circle Englishes.

Berns counted papers published in two scholarly journals, World Englishes and English.

Today, and found that within the period of 1998–2001 these journals published

47 articles on Expanding Circle Englishes.

In 2001–2018, the number of papers on Expanding Circle Englishes was 318.

The total number was 365 papers covering 79 countries and 11 regions, with the “lion’s share” (Berns 2019: 12) relating to East Asia, especially China (about 100 papers) and Japan (20 papers)

In fact, the proof of her statement can be seen even in such encyclopedic reference works as handbooks.

The first Handbook of World Englishes, published in 2006 (Kachru, Kachru & Nelson 2006), had only three chapters on Expanding Circle varieties – East Asian, South American, and European Englishes – of sixteen chapters describing localized world Englishes.

All the problems are discussed from international perspectives, as the authors have worked in different parts of the world and synthesized their empirical research with in-depth theoretical foundations. We hope that readers will find the issues raised in these papers to be useful and stimulating food for thought, further research, and practical activities.